

Larvicidal Activity Validation of *Scorodophloeus zenkeri* Harms and *Garcinia mangostana* L. from Democratic Republic of the Congo using *Culex quinquefasciatus* (Diptera: Culicidae) as model system

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ABSTRACT:

The emergence of mosquitos' resistance to synthetic insecticides constitutes a public health challenge in endemic areas. Insecticides of plant origin may serve as an alternative bio-control technique. The aim of this study was to evaluate the bioactivity of aqueous extracts of *G. mangostana* and *S. zenkeri* on *Cx. quinquefasciatus* larva. Larvicidal bioassays were carried out according to WHO protocol. The results showed that *S. zenkeri* is more larvicidal than *G. mangostana*. Aqueous extract of *S. zenkeri* displayed a very good larvicidal activity than *G. mangostana* with 90% mortality rate at 50% of extract dose after 24 hours exposure ($LC_{50} = 32.5 \pm 5.8$ mg/l and $LC_{90} = 47.7 \pm 6.2$ mg/l). The present finding indicates that selection of plant through zoopharmacognosy approach can serve as source of promising botanical mosquito control agents (which are biodegrade and environmentally no persistent) to be proposed as alternative to the conventional larvicides. For the best of our knowledge, this is the first report on the larvicidal activity of *S. zenkeri* from Democratic Republic of the Congo in the literature using *Culex quinquefasciatus* as model system.

Keyword: Zoopharmacognosy, Medicinal plants, Biopesticides, mosquito-borne diseases control, public health.

INTRODUCTION:

Mosquitoes are important insects of medical relevance and are considered major public health pests [1]. They transmit many diseases to humans and other vertebrates [2]. Mosquitoes belonging to the genera *Culex* are transmitting Japanese encephalitis and filariasis. The mosquito species *Culex quinquefasciatus* Say is the most important vector of *Wuchereria bancrofti* the causative agent of lymphatic filariasis [3, 4]. Recent reports indicate that synthetic pesticides have been widely used against mosquitoes which have been conducted to the development of resistance to chemical insecticides and to vectorial capacity rebound. Others side effects of synthetic chemicals like environmental pollution and toxic hazards to humans and other no target organisms created awareness of the need for eco-friendly and target-specific pesticides for a efficient mosquito control [5, 6]. Medicinal plant species may be alternative sources of mosquito control agents. Indeed, it is proven that natural products are eco-friendly, target-specific, less expensive, and highly efficacious pesticides for the control of vector mosquitoes [7, 8]. Secondary metabolites of plant origin can induce death to insects while trying to consume them either by perturbing the function of nerves or digestive system or by stopping the larva growth [9]. Tropical areas (including Democratic Republic of the Congo) were mosquito-borne diseases are endemic constitute a risk regions for contracting arthropod-borne illnesses [10]. It is therefore necessary to control

mosquitoes in order to prevent mosquito-borne diseases for the improvement of public health.

The present study was undertaken with the aim of validating the larvicidal activity of *Scorodophloeus zenkeri* Harms (Leguminosae) and *Garcinia mangostana* L. (Clusiaceae) from Democratic Republic of the Congo using *Cx. quinquefasciatus* mosquitoes (Diptera: Culicidae) as model system. *Scorodophloeus zenkeri* Harms is a tropical tree of Central Africa. It is of restricted height with a trunk diameter rarely exceeding 80 cm. The tree has garlic-like odor which comes from its sulphur containing compounds. The bark, seeds and wood of *Scorodophloeus zenkeri* are used as spices in some traditional dishes and also in folk medicine for the treatment of several diseases [11]. The plant species is consumed by great apes like *Pan paniscus* [12]. Some compounds as sulphoxides (2,3,5-trithiahexane 5-oxide and 2,4,5,7-tetrathiaoctane 2-oxide) and sulphones [*S*-(methylthiomethyl)methanesulfonothioate, methylthio(methylthio-methyl)sulfone, 2,3,5,7-tetrathiaoctane3,3-dioxide, methylsulphonylmethylthiomethane, methylmethanethiosulfonate, bis-methyl-sulphonylmethane, and bis-(methylthiomethyl)sulfone] were isolated from the bark extracts of *Scorodophloeus zenkeri* Harms [13].

Garcinia mangostana L. belongs to the family of Clusiaceae. The pericarp (peel, rind, hull or ripe) of *G. mangostana* (GM) is used as a traditional medicine for the treatment of abdominal pain, diarrhea, dysentery, infected wound, suppuration, and

chronic ulcer. Experimental studies have demonstrated that extracts of GM have antioxidant, antitumoral, antiallergic, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, and antiviral activities. The pericarp of GM is a source of xanthenes. Some members of these compounds possess antioxidant, antitumor, anti-allergic, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, antifungal and antiviral properties [14]. For the best of our knowledge, this is the first report on the larvicidal activity of *S. zenkeri* and *G. mangostana* from Democratic Republic of the Congo in the literature.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant material collection and identification

The plant species *Scorodophloeus zenkeri* Harms was collected in the Province of Equateur in the Western north of Democratic Republic of the Congo and was identified by comparison with reference specimens available at the Herbarium of the Department of Biology, Faculty of Science (University of Kinshasa). While the fruits of *Garcinia mangostana* L. were purchased from a local market.

Extraction

The plant material was kept at room temperature (25 to 30 °C) for air drying (two week). The air-dried and powdered material was extracted by infusing 20 g of powder of each plant in 200 ml of hot water shaken with a magnetic agitator for 30 minutes and filtered through a Wattman filter paper. All extracts were kept at +25 °C until biological screening for their larvicidal activity.

Phytochemical screening

The dried and powdered plant material (10 g) was repeatedly extracted by cold percolation with 95% ethanol and water (100 mL x 2) for 48 hours. Chemical screening was done as follow [15].

Detection of flavonoids

The ethanol extract (5 ml) was added to a concentrated sulphuric acid (1 ml) and 0.5g of Mg. A pink or red coloration that disappear on standing (3 min) indicates the presence of flavonoids.

Detection of anthocyanosids

The presence of anthocyanosids is revealed by a color change as a function of pH due to titration of the acidic aqueous solution with a solution of NaOH. If the solution turns a red color, the pH is less than 3, if against a blue color; the pH is between 4 and 6.

Detection of tannins

Two methods were used to test for tannins. First, about 1 ml of the ethanol extract was added in 2 ml of water in a test tube. 2 to 3 drops of diluted ferric chloride solution was added and observed for green to blue-green (catechic tannins) or a blue-black (gallic tannins) coloration. Second, 2 ml of the aqueous extract was added to 2 ml of water, a 1 to 2 drops of diluted ferric chloride solution was added. A dark green or blue green coloration indicates the presence of tannins.

Detection of leucoanthocyanins

To 2 ml of aqueous extract was added few drop of Shinoda reagent in a test tube and then boiled. A red or purple coloration in the supernatant indicates the presence of leucoanthocyanins.

Detection of alkaloids

Five ml of the extract was added to 2 ml of HCl. To this acidic medium, 1 ml of Dragendorff's reagent was added. An orange or red precipitate produced immediately indicates the presence of alkaloids.

Detection of saponins

To 1 ml of aqueous extract was added few volume of distilled water in a test tube. The solution was shaken vigorously and observed for a stable persistent froth for 20 min.

Mosquitoes

The mosquito species used for the tests was *Culex quinquefasciatus*. The larvae of this species were collected in some gutters in the commune of Lemba/Kinshasa city and were reared in the laboratory of Physiology of the Department of Biology, Faculty of Science, Kinshasa University (Democratic Republic of Congo). Late 3rd-4th early instar larva of *Cx. quinquefasciatus* were used to screen the biocidal activity of plant extracts.

Larvicidal bioassay

Sensitivity tests were performed according to the World Health Organization protocol (WHO) with minor modifications [16]. Briefly, Ten healthy late third to early fourth instar larvae were introduced into each testing cup, which contained lodging water. A measured volume of stock solution (100 mg/l) was added to obtain the desired concentrations. Experiments were carried out with a series of concentrations ranging from 1 to 50%, each with three replicates, with a final total number of 30 larvae for each concentration. Each batch of replicates contained one control of 10 ml of water alone and another of 10 ml water containing tested extract. After 24 hours exposures the dead larvae were counted. The mortality was recorded after 24 hour of exposure as lethal concentration (LC).

Figure 1: Fruits of *G. mangostana* and barks of *S. zenkeri*; (b) aqueous extracts of tested plants; (c) larval lodging; (d) experimental device

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The phytochemical screening of the two selected plants is given in table 1.

As shown in table 1, tannins and leucoanthocyanins were found in both *S. zenkeri* and *G. mangostana* aqueous extracts while flavonoids and saponins were found only in the bark of *S. zenkeri* and a total absence of anthocyanins, quinones and alkaloids was noticed. But anthocyanins, quinones and alkaloids were found only in the pericarp of *G. mangostana* and a total absence of secondary metabolites like saponins and flavonoids was observed

Table 1: Phytochemical composition of *S. zenkeri* and *G. mangostana*

Chemical compound	<i>S. zenkeri</i>	<i>G. mangostana</i>
Flavonoids	+	-
Anthocyanins	-	+
Tannins	+	+
Leucoanthocyanins	+	+
Quinones	-	+
Alkaloids	-	+
Saponins	+	-

The larvicidal activity of tested plant species is given figure 2.

2a

2b

Figure 2: (a) Larvicidal activity of *S. zenkeri* and *G. mangostana*; (b) Time dependent activity of *S. zenkeri* aqueous extract

Figure 2 revealed that *S. zenkeri* displayed a very good larvicidal activity against *Culex* larva than *G. mangostana* (fig. 2a). The calculated value of LC_{50} (Lethal concentration required to kill 50% of larvae) and LC_{90} (Lethal concentration required to kill 90% of larvae) were 32.5 ± 5.8 mg/l and 47.7 ± 6.2 mg/l respectively. The inhibition of the larvae was more significant

after 36 hours of exposure (fig. 2b). This difference in bioactivity is due to the chemical composition of used plant species especially the plant flavonoids content. These natural products were reported to have inhibitory effect on insect enzymes like cytochrome P-450 dependent ecdysone 20-monooxygenase activity. Flavonoids as plant allelochemicals may function as biopesticides affecting insect ecdysteroidogenesis [17]. The effects of flavonoids on the transhydrogenation, NADH oxidase, and succinate dehydrogenase reactions were also reported authors suggested that compounds of this nature may prove valuable in the control of insect populations by affecting these mitochondrial enzyme components [18]. The mechanisms of action of plant secondary metabolites on insect body were reviewed and include several physiological disruptions, such as inhibition of acetyl cholinesterase, GABA-gated chloride channel, sodium and potassium ion exchange disruption and inhibition of cellular respiration. Such disruption also includes the blockage of calcium channels, of nerve cell membrane action, of octopamine receptors, hormonal balance disruption, mitotic poisoning, disruption of the molecular events of morphogenesis and alteration in the behavior and memory of cholinergic system, etc. Of these, [19] reported that the most important activity is the inhibition of acetyl cholinesterase activity as it is a key enzyme responsible for terminating the nerve impulse transmission through synaptic pathway. Anoupam and coworkers [20] reported that flavonoids have a dilating capacity that can make integument cells of insects permeable to bioactive metabolites such as essential oils that can alter the neurotransmitter system of insects by inhibiting the acetyl cholinesterase leading to the accumulation of acetylcholine in insect tissues and causes paralysis and even death. The chemical screening analysis revealed the absence of flavonoids in aqueous extract of *G. mangostana*. But the feeble activity of this extract observed should be due to the presence of xanthenes which are chemical markers of Clusiaceae family. The high bioactivity displayed by *S. zenkeri* could be due to both flavonoids and volatile sulfur-containing compounds [12, 13]

CONCLUSION

The aim of this study was to evaluate the bioactivity of aqueous extracts of *G. mangostana* and *S. zenkeri* on *Cx. quinquefasciatus* larva. The results showed that *S. zenkeri* is more larvicidal than *G. mangostana*. Further studies are needed in order to test flavonoids alone or in combination with essential oils for a better understanding the contribution of these chemical groups in the larvicidal activity of *S. zenkeri*. The present finding indicates that selection of plant through zoopharmacognosy approach can serve as source of promising botanical mosquito control agents (which are biodegrade and environmentally no persistent) to be proposed as alternative to the conventional larvicides.

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